

Synthesis of Magnetic Nanoparticles Using Potato Extract for Dye Degradation: A Green Chemistry Experiment

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1. PRE-LABORATORY ASSIGNMENT

- a. Define the following terms:
 - Green Chemistry
 - Nanoparticles
 - Reducing Agents
 - Stabilizing Agents
- b. What are the principles of green chemistry?
- c. What are magnetic materials? What are the various classes of magnetic materials?
- d. Describe the structure of Fe_3O_4 .
- e. Discuss the important applications of magnetic materials.
- f. What is the composition and structure of starch?
- g. Discuss the importance of dyes in daily life.
- h. Explain the structure of Rhodamine B dye.
- i. What are the harmful effects of dyes on environment?
- j. Discuss the principles and working of UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

2. BACKGROUND

Advances in the area of green and sustainable chemistry has led to the active development of nanotechnology. Among metal oxide NPs, major efforts are invested on MNPs as they can be easily manipulated using external magnet.¹ The salient features of MNPs have been summarized in figure S1. Several physical and chemical methods have been developed till date for the synthesis of MNPs; however, due to the use of toxic and expensive reagents, high energy requirements and formation of harmful by-products, the focus has now shifted towards the designing of clean and environmentally benign synthetic protocols.²

Insoluble in reaction media	Advantages of Magnetic Nanoparticles	Facile detection
Wide applications	High surface reactivity	High thermal stability
Good recyclability Fast magnetic recovery		Easy to tailor properties

Figure S1. Features of magnetic nanoparticles.

In this context, a wide variety of biological resources (plants and microorganisms) have been used for the synthesis of MNPs (Table S1). Some of the green advantages of using these biological resources include development of clean and eco-friendly method that replaces harsh reducing and capping agents with natural and safe alternatives, use of non-toxic reagents, and reduced overall cost.

Table S1. Some biological resources used for the synthesis of MNPs.

S.No.	Source	Function	Morphology and size	Reference
1.	Green tea (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>) leaves extract	Reducing and stabilizing agent	Spherical; 60 nm	3
2.	Rambutan peel waste extract	Green ligation and chelating agent	Spinel; 100-200 nm	4
3.	Urease enzyme	Multifunctional reagent; including catalyst, template and dispersant	Nanospheres; 19 ± 5 nm	5
4.	Caffeine	Base; to alkalinize the medium	Spherical; 9.72 ± 0.15 nm	6
5.	<i>Euphorbia condylocarpa</i> M. bieb root extract	Reducing and stabilizing agent	less than 39 nm	7
6.	Soya bean sprouts	Bio-template	Spherical; 8 nm	8
7.	Potato extract	Reducing and stabilizing agent	Cubic; 40 nm	9
8.	Black plum (<i>Syzygium</i>	Green solvent, reducing and capping agent	Spherical; 9-20 nm	10

	<i>cumin</i>) seed extract			
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Nature and Characteristics of Superparamagnetic NPs

Magnetite nanoparticles has the cubic inverse spinel structure containing two Fe^{3+} and one Fe^{2+} ions. Oxygen atoms form fcc closed-pack structure where half of Fe^{3+} ions occupy tetrahedral sites whereas other half and Fe^{2+} ions occupy octahedral sites. Thus, Fe_3O_4 can be denoted as $(\text{Fe}^{3+})_{\text{Td}}(\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{Fe}^{2+})_{\text{Oh}}\text{O}_4^{2-}$.¹¹ Based on the arrangement of unpaired electrons, Fe_3O_4 NPs can demonstrate ferromagnetic, antiferromagnetic or ferrimagnetic behavior.¹² In 1930, Frenkel and Dorfman introduced the concept of superparamagnetism.¹³ A superparamagnetic material is the one that shows paramagnetic behavior below the Curie temperature of its bulk material. Iron oxide NPs show superparamagnetism when their size become very small and thermal fluctuations can alter the direction of magnetization in the whole crystal. Magnetite NPs exhibit superparamagnetic behavior at room temperature, thus showing zero coercivity, zero remanence and no hysteresis. This means that when the external magnetic field is switched off, the magnetic domains align randomly giving zero resultant magnetization. Due to these features, magnetic nanoparticles are widely used in biomedical fields such as targeted drug delivery, bioimaging, hyperthermia, photoablation therapy, biosensors, and theranostics applications.¹⁴

3. STUDENT HANDOUT

Objective: (a) To synthesize magnetic nanoparticles using starch-rich potato extract and to study their properties using various characterization techniques; (b) To investigate the application of magnetic nanoparticles in the degradation of organic dye using Rhodamine B as a model compound

Estimated Lab Time: 2 laboratory sessions with 3 hours duration each

Experimental Procedure:

1. Green synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles using potato extract (First lab period):

a) Preparation of potato extract:

1. Weigh 15 g of freshly chopped potato. Wash it several times with distilled water to remove dust particles.

2. Place the washed potatoes under sunlight for a day to remove the residual water.

3. Transfer the dried potatoes in a conical flask containing 200 mL of distilled water and a stirring bar. Boil the solution for 10 minutes under constant stirring.

4. Allow the solution to cool to room temperature. After that filter the resultant solution using Whatman filter paper no. 1.

5. Collect the obtained pale-yellow colored starch-rich potato extract.

b) Synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles:

1. Take 40 mL of potato extract in a round bottom flask. Add a stir bar and place it on a magnetic stir plate.

2. Weigh 3.0 g of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

3. Transfer the weighed amount of salt in the round bottom flask containing potato extract.

4. Heat the solution at 80 °C until a deep yellow color is obtained.

5. Sonicate the resultant deep-yellow solution for 15 minutes at room temperature.

6. After 15 minutes, place the flask again on the stir plate.
7. Next, adjust the pH of the solution to 8.0 by adding 4M NaOH solution dropwise. The color of the solution will immediately turn from yellow to greenish-black. Allow the mixture to stir for additional 20 minutes at 85 °C to obtain deep black colored MNPs.

8. Pour the solution in a beaker and place it above an external magnet for the separation of MNPs. Now, wash the particles thoroughly with distilled water until the pH becomes neutral.

9. Decant the water. Finally, dry the obtained MNPs in oven at 70 °C and finely crush them using a pestle-mortar.

2. Degradation of Rhodamine B Organic Dye (second lab period):

a) Preparation of standard solutions:

Concept:

• Parts Per Million (ppm) is a measurement of the concentration of a solution. • 1 ppm is one part by weight, or volume, of solute in 1 million parts by weight, or volume, of solution.

$$1 \text{ ppm} = 1\text{g} / \text{m}^3 = 1 \text{ mg} / \text{L} = 1 \mu\text{g} / \text{mL}$$

(i) Preparation of 1 L, 100 ppm stock solution of Rhodamine B dye (sufficient for whole class):

$$100 \text{ ppm of RhB} = \text{weight of the dye required (mg)} / 1 \text{ (L)}$$

Weight of the dye required = 100 mg

(ii) Dilution:

Dilute the stock solution to prepare 50 mL of 10 ppm dye solution (required by each student), which will be used in degradation experiment.

Apply the dilution formula:

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$$

(C_1 and V_1 are concentration and volume of stock solution respectively while C_2 and V_2 are respective concentration and volume of the solution needs to be prepared)

$$\text{so, } 100 * V_1 = 10 * 50$$
$$V_1 = 5 \text{ mL}$$

(iii) Preparation of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution:

Molarity (C) of H₂SO₄ with assay 97-99% is 18.35 M.

Apply the dilution formula $C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$ to prepare 10 mL of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ solution.

b) Degradation Procedure

1. Dilute the 100 ppm rhodamine B stock solution (provided by teacher) to obtain 50 mL of 10 ppm dye solution. For this, pipette out the calculated volume (5 mL) of stock solution in a 50 mL standard flask and make up the volume.

Dilution

100 ppm 10 ppm

2. Adjust the pH of prepared 10 ppm dye solution to 5.0 by adding a few drops of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ and checking *via* a simple pH paper.

3. Take 7 glass vials and label them as 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 min.

4. Pipette out 3 mL of 10 ppm acidified dye solution in each glass vial. 5. Add 10 mg of synthesized MNPs and 0.2 mL of 30% aqueous H_2O_2 solution into each vial.

6. Place the vials in an ultrasonic bath, maintained at a temperature of 55 °C.

7. At regular intervals of time, take out the respective vial and place it over an external magnet to separate the MNPs.
8. Measure the absorbance of each solution using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

c) Measurements: Record the UV-visible spectrum of solutions collected at different time intervals in the wavelength range of 400-700 nm. On increasing the contact time, the color and absorbance of the solutions decreases and complete degradation of dye is achieved in 30 minutes (Figure S2). Plot the obtained data using Microsoft excel taking wavelength on the abscissa and absorbance on the ordinate to see the effect of contact time on dye degradation.

Figure S2. Color of the RhB dye solutions at different intervals of time.

d) Calculation of % degradation of dye:

To calculate percentage degradation, use Lambert-Beer law:

$$A = \log_{10} (I_0/I) = \epsilon cl$$

A = Absorbance

I_0 = Initial light intensity

I = Light intensity after it passes through the sample

ϵ = Molar extinction coefficient

c = Concentration (mol/dm^3)

l = Path length (cm)

$$\% \text{ degradation} = (\text{initial concentration} - \text{concentration of solution at time } t / \text{initial concentration of solution}) * 100$$

$$= (\text{initial absorbance} - \text{absorbance of solution at time } t / \text{initial absorbance of solution}) * 100$$

Learning Outcomes:

At the end of the two sessions experiment, students will be able to:

- Apprehend the concept of green chemistry and nanotechnology.
- Appreciate the use of a routinely consumable vegetable, potato, as a chemical reagent for the synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles.
- Prepare solutions of desired concentrations at ppm levels and learn dilution techniques using basic concentration calculations.
- Manage and plot the data using Microsoft Excel.
- Understand the relationship between absorbance of a colored solution and concentration of the substance using UV-Vis spectrophotometer.
- Learn to characterize a material using analytical instruments such as FT-IR. • The dye degradation experiment opens a door for the discussion of finding sustainable solutions to real environmental problems in a simple undergraduate/graduate laboratory.

4. INSTRUCTOR'S NOTES

The purpose of this study is to develop a systems and cyclic thinking approach amongst students. Therefore, teachers are advised to instruct according to the systems thinking hierarchical model, as mentioned in the main article.

Estimated Lab Time: 2 laboratory sessions with 3 hours duration each

Session 1: In the beginning of the laboratory session, discuss the concept of nanotechnology, principles of green chemistry and the merits of integration of both. Elaborate the structure and magnetic properties of iron oxide NPs. Every student will perform experiment individually, but the characterization of MNPs can be performed in a group of two or more where they will record the FT-IR spectrum of the NPs in the wavenumber range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Session 2: In the beginning of the second laboratory session, discuss the important applications of dyes in our daily life. Elaborate the structure, properties and harmful effects of Rhodamine B dye on human health and environment. This experiment can be performed in a group of two. The UV-Visible spectra of the solutions will be recorded in the wavelength range of 400-700 nm.

(a) Materials

S. No.	Item	Comment
1.	Conical flask (500 mL)	Reaction vessel (pre-cleaned)

2.	Round bottom flask (100 mL)	Reaction vessel (pre-cleaned)
3.	Beaker (250 mL & 100 mL)	Reaction vessel (pre-cleaned)
4.	Glass vials (5 mL)	Reaction vessel (for dye degradation experiment)
5.	Measuring cylinder (100 and 10 mL)	To transfer distilled water and to prepare 4M NaOH solution, respectively
6.	Standard flask (50 mL)	To prepare dye solutions
7.	Funnel and Whatman filter paper no. 1	For filtration
8.	Spatula	For adding FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O
9.	Graduated pipette	For adding aqueous H ₂ O ₂
10.	Magnetic stir bar	For stirring
11.	Magnetic stir hot plate	To heat the solutions
12.	Dropper	For adding NaOH
13.	pH paper	To adjust pH
14.	External magnet	To separate magnetic nanoparticles from solution
15.	Pestle-mortar	To crush magnetic nanoparticles
16.	Dried potatoes	Dried potatoes should be provided to students, since it requires a complete day to be dried under sunlight.

(b) CAS Registry Numbers

S. No.	Chemical	Company	CAS Number
1.	Ferrous sulfate heptahydrate (FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O)	Thomas Baker Pvt. Ltd.	7782-63-0
2.	Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	Thomas Baker Pvt. Ltd.	1310-73-2
3.	Rhodamine B dye	Sigma-Aldrich	81-88-9
4.	Sulfuric acid (H ₂ SO ₄)	Fisher Scientific	7664-93-9
5.	Hydrogen peroxide (H ₂ O ₂)	Fisher Scientific	7722-84-1

(c) Characterization Techniques Used

S. No.	Characterization Technique	Details of the Instrument	Comment
1.	FT-IR	Shimadzu IRAffinity-1S	For analyzing the surface functional groups on MNPs
2.	XRD	Rigaku Cu (K α ; λ = 1.5406 Å) diffractometer, scanning rate= 4° min ⁻¹ , 2 θ range= 15-90°	To determine the crystallinity of MNPs
3.	EDS coupled SEM	JEOL Japan Mode: JSM 6610LV microscope	For determining surface morphology of MNPs and elemental composition
4.	TEM	FEI TECHNAI G2 T20 operated at 200 kV Sample preparation: Disperse the sample in ethanol and drop cast it on a copper grid coated with an amorphous carbon film	To analyze the shape and size of MNPs
5.	VSM	Microsense, Model ADE – EV9	To determine the magnetic properties of MNPs
6.	UV-Vis	Motras Scientific UV Plus	To record the absorbance values of dye solutions

(d) Tips and Troubleshooting Notes**• During the synthesis of MNPs**

- Potatoes used in the synthesis must be fresh.
- Potatoes must be cleaned thoroughly with distilled water.
- Freshly prepared potato extract must be used.
- Glassware must be thoroughly cleaned.
- NaOH solution must be added drop-wise while adjusting the pH to 8.

□ Double distilled water must be used throughout the experiment.

• **During the MNP catalyzed degradation of dye**

- pH of the dye solution must be accurately adjusted to 5.0.
- Temperature must be maintained at 55 °C during sonication.
- Sonication must be performed under air. Do not cover vials during sonication.
- Vials must be removed at correct intervals of time.
- Cuvettes must be properly cleaned.

(e) Safety Considerations

Safety is the prime concern in any chemical laboratory. So, instruct students to wear safety aprons, protective glasses, shoes and disposable gloves throughout the experiment. H_2O_2 is a corrosive oxidizer and on direct contact will irritate skin.

(f) Characterizations of Magnetic Nanoparticles:

The synthesized MNPs are examined using various characterization techniques to determine morphology, size, functionalization, composition, and magnetization values.

Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopic Analysis (FT-IR):

FT-IR spectroscopic technique is employed to identify the functional groups present in a molecule. FT-IR spectrum of MNPs has been shown in figure S3. A sharp Fe-O stretching vibration at 543.8 cm^{-1} confirms the synthesis of Fe_3O_4 NPs. A broad absorption band in range of $3450\text{-}3180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the O-H stretching vibration originating from starch. Furthermore, broadness of this peak suggests the formation of intensive intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The peaks at 1379 and 1651 cm^{-1} correspond to the vibrations from C-H bending and adsorbed water respectively. While peak at 1030 cm^{-1} is due to C-O ether bond of the glucose ring.⁹

Figure S3. FT-IR spectrum of Fe_3O_4 NPs.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD):

The crystalline nature of MNPs is investigated using XRD studies (Figure S4). The peaks at 2θ values of 29.97° , 35.38° , 42.9° , 56.78° , 62.33° , and 74.15° correspond to the (2 2 0), (3 1 1), (4 0

0), (5 1 1), (4 4 0), and (5 3 3) crystal planes. These peaks match perfectly with the standard Fe₃O₄ XRD pattern having face centered cubic structure (JCPDS card no. 88-0866).¹⁵ Moreover, no additional peak is observed in the spectrum, suggesting the high purity of synthesized NPs.

Figure S4. XRD spectrum of MNPs.

Calculation of crystallite size from XRD

To calculate the crystallite size, use Scherrer equation

$$D = 0.9 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

D = Crystallite size in Å

λ = X-ray wavelength; 1.5418 Å for Cu Kα Radiation

β = Full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the highest intensity peak, in Radians

θ = Peak position (2θ)

To calculate the size of MNPs, substitute the obtained values of β and θ in the above equation (In the current case, $D = 0.9 * 1.5418 / \{0.0141 * \cos (35.38/2)\} = 258.301 \text{ Å} = 25.83 \text{ nm}$)

Electron Microscopic Analysis:

In order to have insight about the morphology and size of the as-synthesized MNPs, scanning electron microscopic (SEM) and transmission electron microscopic (TEM) analysis are conducted. SEM image of MNPs (Figure S5) reveals that the nanoparticles have nearly uniform spherical shape. Figure S6 shows the TEM images of MNPs at different scale bars. TEM images illustrate that MNPs are well dispersed with the particle size of 20-30 nm.

Figure S5. SEM image of MNPs.

(a) (b) (c)

Figure S6. TEM images of MNPs at different scale bars.

Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopic Analysis (EDS):

EDS survey of MNPs confirms the presence of iron and oxygen in Fe_3O_4 NPs (Figure S7).

Figure S7. EDS spectrum of MNPs.

Vibrating Sample Magnetometry (VSM):

The magnetic property of NPs is investigated by using a vibrating sample magnetometer at room temperature. As can be seen from figure S8, the S-shaped curve with negligible coercivity or remanence suggest the superparamagnetic nature of the NPs. Also, the NPs demonstrate sufficiently high saturation magnetization (M_s) value of 74.4 emu g^{-1} . Due to high M_s value, the MNPs are effectively separated from the solution within 20 seconds.

Figure S8. Room temperature magnetization curve of MNPs.

(g) MNPs catalyzed degradation of rhodamine B dye:

Optimizations:

For determining the best conditions, we carried out some control experiments and varied some parameters including amount of MNPs and H_2O_2 .

Control Experiments:

To demonstrate the role of Fe_3O_4 NPs, H_2O_2 and ultrasonication, some control experiments are performed using RhB dye as a model substrate (Figure S9). It can be observed that in the absence of Fe_3O_4 NPs, degradation of RhB is very low (12.23 %). This proves the necessity of MNPs in the degradation process. Next, to check the importance of H_2O_2 , we placed a glass vial containing only dye solution and MNPs under sonication for 30 minutes. Surprisingly, only 8.5 % degradation took place. This result confirms the importance of H_2O_2 in the degradation. In another experiment, mixture containing dye solution, H_2O_2 and MNPs is magnetically stirred on a stirrer for 1 hour. The result indicates that ultrasonication also plays a crucial role as degradation is comparatively low (40 %). On the other hand, the $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{US}$ system is found to be very effective for the degradation and more than 99 % of the dye is degraded in just 30 minutes.

a

Figure S9. Control experiments showing the role of each element in the degradation procedure. (3.0 mL RhB solution, pH = 5.0, 55 °C, 30 min.^a 1 h. Take 10 mg Fe_3O_4 NPs, 0.2 mL H_2O_2 solution (30 %), ultrasonication wherever applicable).

Effect of MNP loading:

The effect of loading of MNPs on the degradation of RhB is shown in figure S10. It can be seen that, with the increase in amount of MNPs from 2 mg to 10 mg, the degradation of RhB increases. Also, 10 mg is the optimized amount for the degradation. MNPs behave as peroxidase-like radical species and hence improve degradation.¹⁶

catalyst that accelerate the decomposition of H_2O_2 which in turn generates strong oxidizing

Figure S10. Effect of MNPs loading on the degradation of RhB. (3.0 mL RhB solution, 0.1 mL H_2O_2 solution (30 %), ultrasonication, pH = 5.0, 55 °C, 30 min)

Effect of amount of H₂O₂:

We also studied the effect of amount of H₂O₂ on the degradation of RhB. As can be seen from figure S11, the concentration of H₂O₂ plays a crucial role in the degradation. As the amount of H₂O₂ increases from 0.05 mL to 0.20 mL, the absorbance of dye solution decreases. On further increasing the concentration, degradation ability of MNP+H₂O₂+US system decreases. This decrease is explained on the basis of reduced adsorption of RhB on the surface of MNPs due to unfavorable competition between H₂O₂ and dye molecules. Moreover, at higher concentrations the probability of combination of the reactive radicals increases, resulting in the decreased availability of the reactive radicals for substrate oxidation.¹⁶⁻¹⁷

Figure S11. Effect of amount of H₂O₂ on the degradation of RhB. (3.0 mL RhB solution, 10 mg Fe₃O₄ NPs, ultrasonication, pH = 5.0, 55 °C, 30 min)

Recyclability of magnetic nanoparticles:

To imbibe the essence of recycling and sustainability amongst students, we carried out recyclability experiments with MNPs in the catalytic degradation of RhB dye under optimized parameters. At the end of each cycle, the MNPs were separated from the reaction mixture with the help of an external magnet, washed with water and ethanol, dried, and reused in subsequent runs. Figure S12 depicts that even after 4th run, 87% degradation of RhB dye was achieved under optimized conditions.

Figure S12. Recyclability of MNPs in the catalytic degradation of RhB dye.

Green Benefits:

The current experiment offers various green benefits such as:

- Use of easily available, safe, cheap and renewable resource; potato
- Convenient, clean, time-saving and eco-friendly synthetic approach that requires neither harsh conditions nor extra modifiers
- Use of potato extract as green solvent, reducing and capping agent, thereby eliminating the use of toxic chemicals
- Less waste generation
- Does not require high pressure, so significant energy saving
- MNPs, along with an oxidant H₂O₂ and US, served as catalyst for degradation of RhB dye

under ambient conditions

• $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{US}$ system results in almost complete removal of dye (>99%) in just 30 minutes

To our delight, the experiment utilizes nearly seven principles of green chemistry (Figure S13).

Figure S13. Green principles that have been utilized during the two experiments.

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